

Chapter 2 - A pipeline for gene family inference in green algal transcriptomes

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“Produci, consuma, crepa

Produci, consuma, crepa

Produci, consuma, crepa

Sbattiti, fatti, crepa

Sbattiti, fatti, crepa

Sbattiti, fatti, crepa

Cotonati i capelli, riempiti di borchie, rompiti le palle, rasati i capelli

Crepa, crepa, crepa”

CCCP - Morire

³ Authors contribution: A.D.C., K.V.: study design; A.D.C.: data analysis; F.B.: TRAPID plugin and PLAZA4.0 build; A.D.C.: manuscript conceptualization, drafting and writing.

Abstract

In this work we build a semi-automated pipeline for filtering and annotating *de novo* assembled transcriptomic data, using algal datasets as a test case. We further evaluated the relationships between depth of sequencing and transcriptome completeness and also assessed the impact of different partial (transcriptomic) data in the inference of gene families by state-of-the-art phylogenomic pipelines. Since gene family inference was robust and did not suffer from partial transcriptomic data, phylotranscriptomics downstream analyses are expected to be reliable. However, *de novo* assembled transcriptomes seemed to overestimate the size of inferred gene families, suggesting that precautions should be taken before using transcriptomic data in gene family expansion, gain or loss analyses. Our pipeline had been created for green algal transcriptomic data (e.g.: green algal genomes were used to populate reference databases; green algae alternative nuclear genetic code and chloroplast translation tables were taken into account), but it can easily be adapted for analyses of other lineages. This pipeline represents a contribution to a wider, more general purpose: a flexible and user-friendly workflow to address transcriptomic data, annotation and downstream analyses in the absence of reference genomes. Such tool is fundamental to make phylotranscriptomic analyses accessible to those researchers who lack bioinformatics knowledge or access to large computing infrastructures.

Introduction

To date, the available green algal genome sequences suffer from sparse taxon sampling, and many major lineages of core Chlorophyta are not represented at all. A remarkable example is the absence of publicly available genome sequences for ulvophyceans, except for the recent publication of *Ulva mutabilis* genome (De Clerck *et al.*, 2018). The clades for which genomic sequences are available often center on economically relevant species, e.g. production of biofuel and second metabolites by Chlorellales and Trebouxiophyceae (Blanc *et al.*, 2012; Nelson *et al.*, 2017; Roth *et al.*, 2017), or on specific molecular features, e.g. dynamics of genome reduction in prasinophytes (Derelle *et al.*, 2006; Palenik *et al.*, 2007; Worden *et al.*, 2009) and evolution of multicellularity in volvocine green algae (Chlorophyceae) (Merchant *et al.*, 2007; Prochnik *et al.*, 2010; Hanschen *et al.*, 2016; Featherston *et al.*, 2018). This selectivity is not optimal for broad phylogenomic and comparative analyses. Extensive and taxon-rich transcriptome sequencing initiatives, such as the MMESTP and the 1-KP projects (Keeling *et al.*, 2014; Matasci *et al.*, 2014), populated more neglected clades with transcriptomes, however a rigorous estimate of transcriptome completeness for many sequenced species is missing. Moreover, green seaweeds display a huge range of genome sizes, from 25 Mbp up to more than 2 Gbp (Kapraun, 2007).

To explore an organism's gene space, genome sequencing is not always the most obvious choice, despite being inclusive, due to intrinsic challenges (e.g. availability of high-quality high-molecular weight DNA and haploid cells, the amount of repetitive elements and sequence duplication) and species-specific variability in genome size and complexity (Schatz *et al.*, 2012). Transcriptome sequencing provides a faster and cheaper alternative to genome sequencing, but is only able to capture a portion of the total gene space of an organism. Additional challenges are inherent to *de novo* assembly and annotation of transcriptomes, when a reference genome is not available. The initial RNA purified from cells or tissues is a mixture of RNA species with variable stoichiometry: i.e. mature and immature messenger RNAs, ribosomal RNAs, non-coding RNAs and residual genomic DNA contaminants. The experimental design, the selection and enrichment methods for specific RNA species therefore have a considerable impact on the relative abundance of RNA species. This variability

influences the quality and homogeneity of downstream analysis when the RNA-seq libraries are retrieved from different sources. The ideal scenario would require consistency across all samples for all these parameters (Griffith *et al.*, 2015).

Another layer of complexity is given by currently applied sequencing technologies, which rely either on short Next-generation Sequencing (NGS) reads or on long, noisy Single Molecules Real-Time (SMRT) reads. Despite the rise on SMRT sequencing technologies for transcriptome sequencing, their relative low output in sequenced basepairs compared to NGS sequencing and the higher error rates restrict the use of SMRT to specific studies: e.g. discovery of novel isoforms, alternative splicing and polyadenylations, long non-coding RNAs, and gene fusion (Wang *et al.*, 2016; Liu *et al.*, 2017; An *et al.*, 2018). On the other hand, NGS technologies suffer from their inherently short reads, which makes *de novo* assembly of transcriptomes in the absence of a reference genome a non-trivial task. NGS assemblers face multiple challenges: uneven coverage across the transcriptome and even across transcripts due to alternative isoforms, differential levels of expression and sample heterogeneity (Grabherr *et al.*, 2011; Schulz *et al.*, 2012; Steijger *et al.*, 2013). Additional noise in the dataset arises from sequencing errors.

De novo transcriptome assemblies generally result in a higher number of contigs (reconstructed transcripts) than the actual number of genes coded by the genome (Zhao *et al.*, 2011). The redundancy is caused by the presence of allelic and splice variants, and partial assembly or misassembly of sequences due to sequencing and assembly errors. Depending on the quality of the starting RNA, library prep, depth of sequencing and read length, a considerable amount of assembled transcripts covers only fractions of a gene (Wall *et al.*, 2009). Moreover, a *de novo* assembled transcriptome usually does not cover the whole gene space of an organism, due to differential gene expression in different tissues at different time points and life stages. It is therefore important to have reliable metrics to evaluate the completeness of a transcriptome: i.e. the percentage of gene space represented in the transcriptome and the corresponding gene completeness coverage.

In this work, we build an efficient, semi-automated *de novo* assembly, annotation and gene family inference pipeline for transcriptomes, able to tackle most of the shortcomings and challenges inherent to transcriptomic analyses in the absence of a

reference genome. In building our pipeline, we considered several features to be fundamental for assessing the reliability of comparative and phylogenetic studies based on *de novo* assembled transcriptomes: the ability to discriminate between *bona fide* green algal sequences and contaminants in transcriptomes from uncultured organisms and environmental samples; the ability to detect and correct frameshift errors in transcriptomes generated by different sequencing technologies; the ability to assess the transcriptome completeness. In addition, we evaluated the relationships between depth of sequencing, coverage of the assembled transcripts, transcriptome completeness and number of gene families identified and the impact of transcriptomic data on state-of-the-art genome-based methods for gene family inference.

Results

Based on a dataset of genomes or transcriptomes of 55 species (15 reference genomes and 40 *de novo* assembled transcriptomes for which a reference genome was not available), representing the major clades of the green lineage. All orders of the Ulvophyceae were included (Bryopsidales, Cladophorales, Dasycladales, Ignatiales Oltmannsiellopsidales, Scotinosphaerales Trentepohliales, Ulotrichales and Ulvales, Table 2.1). Below we describe and evaluate a series of critical steps of the transcriptomic pipeline, namely:

- Taxonomic binning. The transcriptomes assembly metrics and taxonomic distribution of transcripts were described.
- Frameshift correction. The detection and correction of potential frameshift transcripts was described.
- Gene space completeness evaluation. The performances of BUSCO, coreGF and eggNOG-mapper in assessing gene space completeness of transcriptomes was evaluated.
- Depth of sequencing: transcriptome completeness and gene family size correlation. The relationship between depth of sequencing, gene space completeness and gene family size was evaluated.
- Effect of partial data on Orthology inference. The effect of using transcriptomic data in genomic-pipelines for orthology inference was evaluated.

Transcriptomes assembly metrics and taxonomic binning

The assembly metrics for the 40 transcriptomes (see Table 2.1) are reported in Table 2.2. Since the corresponding raw reads were not available at the time of the study, *Acrosiphonia* sp., *Blastophysa rhizopus* and *Caulerpa taxifolia* transcriptome assemblies were retrieved from the respective online repositories (Table 2.1). The remaining RNA-seq libraries were assembled in house. RNA-seq data generated with 454 technology (*Botryococcus braunii*, *Chlorokybus atmophyticus* and *Ulva linza*) were

Table 2.1: Datasets used in this study.

In green, ulvophyte transcriptomes; in yellow, other green algal transcriptomes; in orange, publicly available genomes.

species	Class or Order	publication	Mitochondrial genome	Chloroplast genome	source
<i>Caulerpa taxifolia</i>	Bryopsidales	(Ranjan <i>et al.</i> , 2015)	N/A	N/A	SRP041084
<i>Codium fragile</i> [#]	Bryopsidales	N/A	N/A	N/A	TBA
<i>Halimeda discoidea</i> [#]	Bryopsidales	N/A	N/A	N/A	TBA
<i>Ostreobium quekettii</i> [#]	Bryopsidales	N/A	N/A	NC_030629.1	TBA
<i>Blastophysa rhizopus</i>	Chaetosiphonales	(Matasci <i>et al.</i> , 2014)	N/A	N/A	OneKP
<i>Tetraselmis astigmatica</i>	Chlorodendrophyceae	(Keeling <i>et al.</i> , 2014)	N/A	N/A	MMTESP0804
<i>Tetraselmis striata</i>	Chlorodendrophyceae	(Keeling <i>et al.</i> , 2014)	N/A	N/A	MMTESP0817
<i>Acutodesmus acuminatus</i> SAG 38.81	Chlorophyceae	N/A	N/A	N/A	SRR1174737
<i>Chlamydomonas reinhardtii</i>	Chlorophyceae	(Merchant <i>et al.</i> , 2007)	NC_001638.1	NC_005353.1	JGI4.0
<i>Dunaliella tertiolecta</i>	Chlorophyceae	(Keeling <i>et al.</i> , 2014)	N/A	N/A	MMTESP1127
<i>Gonium pectorale</i>	Chlorophyceae	(Hanschen <i>et al.</i> , 2016)	AP012493.1	NC_020438.1	NCBI
<i>Haematococcus pluvialis</i>	Chlorophyceae	(Gao <i>et al.</i> , 2015)	N/A	N/A	SRR2148810
<i>Volvox carteri</i>	Chlorophyceae	(Prochnik <i>et al.</i> , 2010)	N/A	N/A	JGI1.0
<i>Auxenochlorella protothecoides</i>	Chlorellales	(Gao <i>et al.</i> , 2014)	NC_026009.1	KC843975.1	KEGG
<i>Chlorella</i> sp NCG4A	Chlorellales	(Blanc <i>et al.</i> , 2010)	NC_025413.1	KJ718922.1	JGI1.0
<i>Picochlorum oklahomensis</i>	Chlorellales	(Keeling <i>et al.</i> , 2014)	N/A	N/A	MMTESP1330
<i>Boodlea composita</i>	Cladophorales	(Del Cortona <i>et al.</i> , 2017)	MG257829 - MG257880	MG257795 - MG257828	SRR5500908
<i>Cladophora glomerata</i>	Cladophorales	(Matasci <i>et al.</i> , 2014)	N/A	N/A	OneKP
<i>Acetabularia acetabulum</i> [#]	Dasycladales	N/A	N/A	N/A	TBA
<i>Ignatius tetrasporus</i>	Ignatiales	(Matasci <i>et al.</i> , 2014)	N/A	NC_034712.1	OneKP
<i>Oltmannsiellopsis unicellularis</i> [§]	Oltmannsiellopsidales	N/A	N/A	N/A	TBA
<i>Oltmannsiellopsis viridis</i> [#]	Oltmannsiellopsidales	N/A	NC_008256.1	NC_008099.1	TBA
<i>Marsupiomonas</i> sp. [#]	Pedinophyceae	N/A	N/A	KM462870.1	TBA
<i>Pedinomonas minor</i> [#]	Pedinophyceae	N/A	NC_000892.1	NC_016733.1	TBA
Unknown pedinophyte YPF701 [#]	Pedinophyceae	N/A	N/A	N/A	TBA

<i>Bathycoccus prasinos</i>	prasinophytes	(Moreau et al., 2012)	FO082258	FO082259.2	ORCAE
<i>Micromonas pusilla</i>	prasinophytes	(Worden et al., 2009)	FJ858268	FJ858269	JGI2.0
<i>Nephroselmis pyriformis</i>	prasinophytes	(Keeling et al., 2014)	N/A	N/A	MMETSP0034
<i>Ostreococcus tauri</i>	prasinophytes	(Palenik et al., 2007)	CR954200	CR954199	ORCAE
<i>Picocystis salinarum</i>	prasinophytes	(Keeling et al., 2014)	N/A	NC_024828.1	MMETSP0807
<i>Scotinosphaera lemnae</i> [#]	Scotinosphaerales	N/A	N/A	N/A	TBA
<i>Asterochloris</i> sp. Cgr/DA1pho	Trebouxiophyceae	N/A	N/A	N/A	JGI2.0
<i>Botryococcus braunii</i>	Trebouxiophyceae	N/A	NC_027722.1	NC_025545.1	SRR069634
<i>Coccomyxa subellipsoidea</i>	Trebouxiophyceae	(Blanc et al., 2012)	NC_015316.1	NC_015084.1	JGI1.0
<i>Pseudochlorella pringsheimii</i>	Trebouxiophyceae	(Zhang et al., 2014)	N/A	N/A	SRR490104
<i>Trebouxia gelatinosa</i>	Trebouxiophyceae	(Carniel et al., 2016)	N/A	N/A	SRR988248
<i>Cephaleuros parasiticus</i> [§]	Trentepohiales	N/A	N/A	N/A	TBA
<i>Trentepohlia annulata</i> [§]	Trentepohiales	N/A	N/A	N/A	TBA
<i>Trentepohlia jolithus</i>	Trentepohiales	(Li et al., 2014)	N/A	N/A	SRR1044982
<i>Acrosiphonia</i> sp. SAG-127.80	Ulotrichales	(Matasci et al., 2014)	N/A	N/A	OneKP
<i>Phaeophila dendroides</i> [§]	Ulvaes	N/A	N/A	N/A	TBA
<i>Ulva linza</i>	Ulvaes	(Zhang et al., 2012)	NC_029701.1	NC_030312.1	SRR504341
<i>Ulva mutabilis</i>	Ulvaes	(De Clerck et al., 2018)	N/A	N/A	ORCAE
<i>Chara vulgaris</i>	Charophyceae	(Matasci et al., 2014)	NC_005255.1	NC_008097.1	ERR364366
<i>Chlorokybus atmophyticus</i>	Chlorokybophyceae	(Timme et al., 2012)	NC_009630.1	NC_008822.1	SRR064329
<i>Chaetosphaeridium globosum</i>	Coleochaetophyceae	N/A	AF494279.1	NC_004115.1	ERR364369
<i>Coleochaete orbicularis</i>	Coleochaetophyceae	(Ju et al., 2015)	N/A	N/A	SRR1594679
<i>Arabidopsis thaliana</i>	Embryophytes	(The Arabidopsis Genome Initiative, 2000)	Y08501	AP000423	TAIR10
<i>Oryza sativa</i>	Embryophytes	(International Rice Genome Sequencing Project, 2005)	DQ167400	X15901	TIGR6.1
<i>Physcomitrella patens</i>	Embryophytes	(Rensing et al., 2008)	AB251495	AP005672	JGI1.1
<i>Selaginella moellendorffii</i>	Embryophytes	(Banks et al., 2011)	JF338143.1- JF338147.1	HM173080.1	JGI1.0
<i>Klebsormidium flaccidum</i>	Klebsormidiophyceae	(Ju et al., 2015)	KP165386.1	NC_024167.1	SRR1594644

<i>Mesostigma viride</i>	Mesostigmatophyceae	(Ju et al., 2015)	NC_008240.1	NC_002186.1	SRR1594255
<i>Mesotaenium endlicherianum</i>	Zygnematophyceae	N/A	N/A	NC_024169.1	ERR364377
<i>Roya obtusa</i>	Zygnematophyceae	N/A	NC_022863.1	NC_030315.1	ERR364380

#: dataset generated in this study
S: dataset available at (<https://dx.doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.1604778>)
JGI: datasets available at the DOE Joint Genome Institute (<https://genome.jgi.doe.gov/portal/>)
KEGG: datasets available at the Kyoto Encyclopedia of Genes and Genomes (<https://www.genome.jp/kegg/genome.html>)
MIMETSP: datasets available at the Short Read Archive (<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/sra/>)
NCBI: dataset available at the National Center for Biotechnology Information (<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/>)
OneKP: datasets available at (http://www.onekp.com/public_read_data.html)
ORCAE: datasets available at Ghent University (<http://bioinformatics.psb.ugent.be/orcae/>)
SRP, SRR, ERR: datasets available at the Short Read Archive (<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/sra/>)
TAIR: dataset available at The Arabidopsis Information Resource (<https://www.arabidopsis.org/>)
TBA: To be announced, datasets not released yet
TIGR: dataset available at the Rice Genome Annotation Project (<http://rice.plantbiology.msu.edu/>)

assembled with CLC Genomic Workbench. The remaining raw reads were assembled with Trinity after filtering and trimming of low quality reads.

The number of transcripts ranged from 11,627 to 258,663 per library, with an N50 length value between 491 and 3,212 bp. All the assemblies were then clustered with CD-HIT-EST with a similarity cut-off of 97.5%. This resulted in a decrease in transcript number between 0.3 and 36.4%. The percentage of transcripts identified as eukaryotic after a sequence similarity search against the NCBI non-redundant protein database ranged from 18.2 to 75.2%. Such wide variation could be ascribed to a higher amount of genuine bacterial contaminants, the presence of non-coding RNA or lineage-specific and recently evolved genes with no sequence similarity to known proteins. The number of transcripts in the eukaryotic fraction ranged from 6,709 to 67,617, with a N50 length value ranging from 711 bp to 4,066 bp (Table 2.2).

Additional insights on the putative taxonomic distribution of the eukaryotic transcripts and on putative species-specific or potentially contaminating sequences in the transcriptomes comes from the GhostKOALA output. GhostKOALA performs similarity searches (BLASTp) between input translated CDS and an expanded KEGG GENES database that includes a non-redundant set of proteins from fully sequenced genomes and their corresponding KO terms and taxonomic affiliation. For comparison, we analyzed the protein coding fraction of the genomes (CDS) in Table 2.1 in a similar way. In addition to “Plants” sequences (i.e.: sequences assigned to Viridiplantae as taxonomic group, hereafter referred to as “green transcripts”), all the transcripts also had a variable fraction of sequences classified as “Animals”, “Protists”, “Fungi” and “Bacteria”, which could represent *bona fide* contaminants (Figure 2.1). For some Ulvophyceae species, for example *Boodlea composita* and the two *Oltmannsiellopsis* species, less than 50% of the sequences were classified as “Plants”. Interestingly, also sequences from well-characterized genomes (e.g.: *Oryza sativa*) were not classified as “Plants”.

Table 2.2: Summary of the *de novo* transcriptome assembly metrics.

Species	before CD-HIT		after CD-HIT		euk fraction		
	# contigs	N50 (bp)	# contigs	N50 (bp)	#contigs	N50 (bp)	% euk
<i>Acetabularia acetabulum</i>	258,663	759	172,881	766	33,527	1,534	19.4
<i>Acrosiphonia</i> sp.	41,150	1,745	41,009	1,729	14,910	2,225	36.4
<i>Blastophyssa</i> cf. <i>rhizopus</i>	83,017	989	82,410	968	15,021	1,767	18.2
<i>Boodlea composita</i>	91,362	1,198	88,503	1,136	23,350	1,703	26.4
<i>Botryococcus braunii</i>	34,959	1,037	33,512	1,055	12,604	1,385	37.6
<i>Caulerpa taxifolia</i>	57,118	813	57,118	813	28,221	1,162	49.4
<i>Cephaleuros parasiticus</i>	63,443	1,695	55,326	1,567	13,987	2,172	25.3
<i>Chaetosphaeridium globosum</i>	38,126	628	26,456	586	11,770	811	44.5
<i>Chara vulgaris</i>	46,674	491	34,824	478	12,067	711	34.7
<i>Chlorokybus atmophyticus</i>	12,689	1,079	12,519	1,083	8,387	1,176	67.0
<i>Cladophora glomerata</i>	59,069	802	57,226	802	14,592	1,363	25.5
<i>Codium fragile</i>	75,407	1,066	60,707	1,090	30,111	1,387	49.6
<i>Coleochaete orbicularis</i>	207,738	1,708	146,497	1,600	45,236	2,328	30.9
<i>Dunaliella tertiolectica</i>	32,282	1,703	30,179	1,688	12,922	2,104	42.8
<i>Haematococcus pluvialis</i>	11,787	1,788	11,370	1,795	6,709	2,026	59.0
<i>Halimeda discoidea</i>	39,964	1,054	34,097	1,095	15,863	1,411	46.5
<i>Ignatius tetrasporus</i>	59,183	994	58,122	994	20,516	1,518	35.3
<i>Klebsormidium flaccidum</i>	113,738	2,098	74,342	2,146	44,330	2,380	59.6
<i>Marsupiomonas</i> sp.	50,280	1,333	35,846	1,469	17,957	1,773	50.1
<i>Mesostigma viride</i>	165,488	1,541	111,045	1,559	36,397	2,153	32.8
<i>Mesotaenium endlicherianum</i>	87,410	1,015	60,117	967	29,363	1,288	48.8
<i>Nephroselmis pyriformis</i>	73,008	1,310	65,605	1,271	31,044	1,535	47.3
<i>Oltmannsiellopsis unicellularis</i>	79,253	1,258	73,250	1,205	25,933	1,811	35.4
<i>Oltmannsiellopsis viridis</i>	129,713	1,415	102,283	1,345	40,053	1,931	39.2
<i>Ostreobium quekettii</i>	138,329	1,810	111,934	1,861	42,293	2,399	37.8
<i>Pedinomonas minor</i>	34,242	3,212	21,795	3,437	11,922	4,066	54.7
<i>Phaeophila dendroides</i>	135,530	1,785	127,650	1,706	45,339	2,371	35.5
<i>Picochlorum oklahomensis</i>	16,181	1,521	15,258	1,491	10,110	1,733	66.3
<i>Picocystis salinarum</i>	11,627	3,043	9,795	2,891	7,370	3,002	75.2
<i>Pseudochlorella pringsheimii</i>	35,760	751	31,608	669	17,468	829	55.3
<i>Roya obtusa</i>	55,929	950	35,927	935	19,889	1,148	55.4
<i>Scenedesmus acuminatus</i>	132,816	1,117	85,597	1,070	29,820	1,559	34.8
<i>Scotinosphaera lemnae</i>	171,583	1,733	127,230	1,603	31,153	2,328	24.5
<i>Tetraselmis astigmatica</i>	40,880	1,740	38,509	1,729	17,542	2,037	45.6
<i>Tetraselmis striata</i>	45,641	1,073	42,621	1,066	19,350	1,345	45.4
<i>Trebouxia gelatinosa</i>	112,450	2,343	73,026	2,396	35,354	2,875	48.4
<i>Trentepohlia annulata</i>	76,660	1,933	71,010	1,825	13,734	2,653	19.3
<i>Trentepohlia jolithus</i>	257,442	702	196,877	555	67,617	952	34.3
<i>Ulva linza</i>	15,866	1,124	15,253	1,140	8,298	1,342	54.4
Pedinophytes (YPF 701)	47,459	1,927	31,648	2,163	16,418	2,572	51.9

before CD-HIT: transcriptome metrics before sequence clustering with CD-HIT EST

after CD-HIT: transcriptome metrics after sequence clustering with CD-HIT EST

euk fraction: metrics of the eukaryotic fraction

% euk: percentage of transcripts (after CD-HIT) identified as eukaryotic

Figure 2.1: Taxonomic binning as assigned by GhostKOALA.

Pie charts report the proportion of the taxonomic bin assigned to protein-coding genes in the genomes and eukaryotic transcriptome assemblies.

Figure 2.2: Percentage of putative frameshift transcripts and success of frameshift correction by FrameDP.

“Before correction” refers to the percentage of putative frameshift transcripts before the correction step, while “after correction” refers to the percentage of putative frameshift transcripts after the correction step. Black dots indicate outlier values.

Frameshift correction

We processed the 40 transcriptomes (Table 2.1) with the TRAPID pipeline to identify potential frameshift errors (hereafter: frameshift transcripts). Frameshift transcripts were corrected with FrameDP and the rate of success of the frameshift correction step was estimated with a subsequent TRAPID run. Depending on the sequencing technology (Table 2.3), the percentage of putative frameshift transcripts ranged from 0.3 to 18.8%, with a mean value of 4.8% (Figure 2.2). The frameshift correction step had a considerable rate of success (mean value 42.8%), measured as the percentage of the number of frameshift transcripts corrected divided by the number of initial frameshift transcripts. Surprisingly, FrameDP run did not result in any frameshift correction of the 8.9% putative frameshift transcripts of *Trentepohlia annulata*.

Gene space completeness evaluation

Gene space completeness was evaluated for the eukaryotic fraction of the transcriptome assemblies with three complementary strategies: coreGF, BUSCO and eggNOG-mapper.

The coreGF score for most of the transcriptomes analyzed was close to 1 (all the core conserved gene families identified), with the exception of the *Chara vulgaris* and *Haematococcus pluvialis* transcriptomes, which had a lower value (coreGF score 0.75).

Table 2.3: sequencing technology and read depth of sequencing for each transcriptome analysis in this study.

species	Sequencing technology	depth of sequencing
<i>Acetabularia acetabulum</i>	Illumina NextSeq 500	103M 2x150 bp PE
<i>Acrosiphonia</i> sp. SAG-127.80	N/A	N/A
<i>Acutodesmus acuminatus</i> SAG 38.81	Illumina HiSeq 2000	21M 2x101 bp PE
<i>Blastophysa rhizopus</i>	N/A	N/A
<i>Boodlea composita</i>	Illumina NextSeq	32M 2x75 bp PE
<i>Botryococcus braunii</i>	454 GS FLX	1.2M
<i>Caulerpa taxifolia</i>	Illumina HiSeq 2000	178M 2x95 bp PE
<i>Cephaleuros parasiticus</i>	Illumina HiSeq 1000	47M 2x100 bp PE
<i>Chaetosphaeridium globosum</i>	Illumina Genome Analyzer II	8M 2x75 bp PE
<i>Chara vulgaris</i>	Illumina Genome Analyzer II	8M 2x75 bp PE
<i>Chlorokybus atmophyticus</i>	454 GS FLX Titanium	444k
<i>Cladophora glomerata</i>	Illumina HiSeq 2000	12M 2x90 bp PE
<i>Codium fragile</i>	Illumina NextSeq	11M 2x150 bp PE
<i>Coleochaete orbicularis</i>	Illumina HiSeq 1000	44M 2x100 bp PE
<i>Dunaliella tertiolecta</i>	Illumina HiSeq 2000	32M 2x50 bp PE
<i>Haematococcus pluvialis</i>	Illumina HiSeq 2500	12M 2x100 bp PE
<i>Halimeda discoidea</i>	Illumina NextSeq	7M 2x150 bp PE
<i>Ignatius tetrasporus</i>	Illumina HiSeq 2000	11M 2x90 bp PE
<i>Klebsormidium flaccidum</i>	Illumina HiSeq 1000	50M 2x100 bp PE
<i>Marsupiomonas</i> sp.	Illumina NextSeq	19M 2x150 bp PE
<i>Mesostigma viride</i>	Illumina HiSeq 1000	47M 2x100 bp PE
<i>Mesotaenium endlicherianum</i>	Illumina HiSeq 2000	13M 2x90 bp PE
<i>Nephroselmis pyriformis</i>	Illumina HiSeq 2000	23M 2x100 bp PE
<i>Oltmannsiellopsis unicellularis</i>	Illumina HiSeq 1000	34M 2x100 bp PE
<i>Oltmannsiellopsis viridis</i>	Illumina NextSeq	26M 2x150 bp PE
<i>Ostreobium quekettii</i>	Illumina NextSeq	24M 2x150 bp PE
<i>Pedinomonas minor</i>	Illumina NextSeq	20M 2x150 bp PE
<i>Phaeophila dendroides</i>	Illumina HiSeq 1000	60M 2x100 bp PE
<i>Picochlorum oklahomensis</i>	Illumina HiSeq 2500	22M 2x50 bp PE
<i>Picocystis salinarum</i>	Illumina HiSeq 2000	16M 2x100 bp PE
<i>Pseudochlorella pringsheimii</i>	Illumina Genome Analyzer IIx	35M 40bp SE
<i>Roya obtusa</i>	Illumina HiSeq 2000	13M 2x90 bp PE
<i>Scotinosphaera lemnae</i>	Illumina NextSeq 500	39M 2x150 bp PE
<i>Tetraselmis astigmatica</i>	Illumina HiSeq 2500	29M 2x50 bp PE
<i>Tetraselmis striata</i>	Illumina HiSeq 2000	20M 2x50 bp PE
<i>Trebouxia gelatinosa</i>	Illumina HiSeq 2000	20M 2x100 bp PE
<i>Trentepohlia annulata</i>	Illumina HiSeq 1000	40M 2x100 bp PE
<i>Trentepohlia jolithus</i>	Illumina HiSeq 2000	26M 2x90 bp PE
<i>Ulva linza</i>	454 GS FLX	251k
Unknown pedinophyte YPF701	Illumina NextSeq	18M 2x150 bp PE

Additional information on the quality of the transcriptome, measured as an estimate of completeness and fragmentation, comes from the percentage of reference genes covered by 50% or 90% of their length by the assembled transcripts (Figure 2.3). While it was possible to identify most of the coreGFs in most of the transcriptomes, those with a score of coreGF close to 1 could have a low coverage score (e.g.: *Caulerpa taxifolia*, *Trentepohlia jolithus*), indicating a partial assembly of the transcripts. For most of the transcriptomes analyzed in this study, at least half of the transcripts covered 50% of the reference gene or more. Furthermore, at least 25% of the transcripts covered 90% of the reference gene (representing a fraction of quasi full-length to full-length transcripts), and represent a promising initial pool of full-length transcripts for downstream phylogenetic analyses. These results were comparable to those from a similar analysis on green transcripts (Figure 2.3).

To avoid a bias toward the number BUSCO genes identified as fragmented, the eukaryotic transcripts were frameshift-corrected before the BUSCO analysis. In total, between 52.8% and 98.3% of eukaryotic BUSCO were identified in the transcriptomes, either as complete, duplicated or fragmented (Figure 2.4). Despite the high variability among the BUSCO results, for most of the transcripts 80-90% BUSCO were identified, indicating a good representation of the conserved core genes in the transcriptomes of our dataset.

The third strategy to assess the gene space completeness of the transcriptomes was based on eggNOG-mapper against three distinct non-supervised orthologous groups (NOG) clusters subsets: Chlorophyta NOGs (chloroNOG), *Viridiplantae* NOGs (virNOG), and all the NOGs present in the database (bacterial and viral NOGs included). The chloroNOG subset is virtually a subset of virNOG KO subset (2675 out of 2677 chloroNOG KO terms are included in virNOG KO terms). ChloroNOG KO terms were well represented in the majority of genomes and transcriptomes analyzed (Figure S2.1), with few notable exceptions (*Blastophyza rhizopus*, *Cladophora glomerata*, and the Trentepohliales *Cephaleuros parasiticus* and *Trentepohlia annulata* – but not *Trentepohlia jolithus*). These observations contrast with the good coreGFs and BUSCO score of these transcriptomes. Similar results were obtained for the virNOG KO terms (Figure S2.2). When compared to the ‘all KO terms collection’, most of the transcriptomes and genomes have comparable patterns of presence/absence of KO

Figure 2.3: GFscore and Reference Coverage score.

Bar plots illustrating the GFscore and the coverage score (50% and 90% of reference genes covered) of the eukaryotic and the green transcripts of each transcriptome.

terms (Figure S2.3). Noticeably, *Trentepohlia jolithus* and *Phaeophila dendroides* seems to have additional KO terms not represented by any of the other genomes/transcriptomes, neither the ones belonging to the same group. This may indicate some degree of non-*Viridiplantae* contaminants in the RNA-seq library. Alternatively, it could indicate events of gain of species-specific functions and lateral gene transfer that were absent in the ancestor and in the other members of the same clade.

Depth of sequencing: transcriptome completeness and gene family size correlation

Depth of sequencing: Transcriptome completeness evaluation

Depth of sequencing influences the amount and the length of transcripts that can be reconstructed in a *de novo* transcriptome assembly, with the underlying assumption that larger RNA-seq libraries are required for representing larger gene spaces. However, for many of the green algal species in this study, little to no info on the corresponding gene space and ploidy level is available. To obtain a good proxy for the minimum depth of sequencing required for detecting full-length transcripts, RNA-seq experiments with increasing sequencing depth were investigated in the model green alga *Chlamydomonas reinhardtii*.

Starting from the same RNA-seq library, ten subsets of reads were randomly selected, ranging from 8M to 80M reads (Table S2.1), to represent RNA-seq experiments with increasing sequencing depth. Each subset was independently *de novo* assembled with Trinity and transcripts clustered. For each assembly, eukaryotic and green transcripts were identified (Figure S2.4, Table S2.1). The completeness of the eukaryotic fraction of the transcriptome assemblies was assessed with three independent strategies: coreGF, BUSCO, eggNOG-mapper (see section 3). The coreGF score for all the assemblies was close to 1, indicating that virtually all the core conserved gene families identified. Increasing sequencing depth resulted in higher fraction of reference genes covered by 50% or 90% of their length (Figure S2.5A).

Figure 2.4: Gene space completeness predicted with the BUSCO analysis.

The bar plot reports the percentage of the BUSCO genes identified as complete, duplicated, fragmented or missing in the assemblies and in the reference genome of the total 303 BUSCO eukaryotic single-gene orthologs.

In total, between 83.9 and 97.3% of eukaryotic BUSCO were identified in the different assemblies (Figure S2.5B), while 98.3% of BUSCO genes were identified in the CDS of the *Chlamydomonas* reference genome v. 5.5. Notably and as expected, at increasing depth of sequencing, more BUSCO genes were identified as complete or duplicated and less as fragmented, indicating that higher depth of sequencing results in longer transcripts and reconstruction of multiple transcripts for each locus.

ChloroNOG KO terms were almost completely covered by the transcripts at all depths of sequencing, as well as virNOG (Figure S2.5C), except for Streptophyta-specific KO terms. When compared to all the NOG available, only a small fraction was identified. A similar analysis performed on the genome indicated discrepancies in the pattern of KO terms identified in the transcriptomes irrespective of the NOG sets analyzed. The presence of additional sequences not covered in the *Chlamydomonas* genome was confirmed by the taxonomic profile obtained with GhostKOALA (Figure S2.4).

Depth of sequencing: gene family size correlation

For each depth of sequencing, gene families were independently build following a PLAZA-like procedure from the coding sequences of 18 Viridiplantae genomes, including reference *Chlamydomonas* sequences and *Chlamydomonas de novo* assembled transcripts (see Materials and Methods for details). Then, in each gene family the number of *Chlamydomonas* reference and *de novo* assembled sequences were evaluated. The analyses of *de novo* eukaryotic transcripts and green transcripts gave comparable results (Figure 2.5, 2.6). The slope of the regression line was slightly below 1 only for the 8M reads subsets. At increasing depth of sequencing, the slope steadily increased, indicating that higher sequencing depth leads to an overestimation of gene family sizes when building gene families from *de novo* assembled transcriptomes. The intercept on the y-axis (expressed eukaryotic transcripts and green transcripts) was always higher than 0, suggesting, in general, a higher number of eukaryotic transcripts than actual genomic genes per gene families. As indicated by the correlation coefficient this trend is subject to considerable variation between gene families (Figure 2.5, 2.6).

Figure 2.5: Gene family size correlation – expressed transcripts.

Each circle represents one or more gene family, the x-axis represents the number of genes from the reference *Chlamydomonas* transcriptome found expressed in that gene family, while the y-axis reports the corresponding genes found in the eukaryotic fraction of the *de novo* assembled transcriptomes. The size of the circle is proportional to the gene families with that relative number of genomic and transcriptomic genes. The blue line corresponds to the regression line, the surrounding grey area indicates the 95% confidence interval. The corresponding equation is reported, together with the coefficient of correlation r^2 .

Effect of partial data on orthology inference

Despite the dataset in this study is composed by a majority of potentially fragmented data (i.e.: *de novo* assembled transcriptomes), the orthology inference was performed with PLAZA 4.0 (Van Bel *et al.*, 2018), a comparative genomic pipeline, designed to deal with a set of comprehensive full-length sequences for gene families delineation. The 40 transcriptomes and 15 genomes of Viridiplantae species present in Table 2.1 were used to build a custom PLAZA 4.0 instance (chloroPLAZA), with more than 70% of the data represented by potentially fragmented data. Therefore, we tested the impact of partial sequences on the inference of homologous gene families by the PLAZA pipeline. In order not to overestimate gene families with perfect correlation, we further filtered out HOM families composed by species-specific genes (“orphan” genes). Then, we performed pairwise comparisons between the three PLAZA builds - picoPLAZA (Vandepoele *et al.*, 2013), PLAZA 2.5, and chloroPLAZA - to assess the distribution of corresponding HOM families on different PLAZA builds and test if unitary gene families were split in different PLAZA builds (Figure 2.7). picoPLAZA against PLAZA 2.5 pairwise comparisons between gave comparable results, with less than 10% of the gene families split into 2 distinct gene families in the second PLAZA build (gene family correlation score of 0.5), while more than 90% of the gene families had a perfect a one to one correspondence (gene family correlation score of 1). chloroPLAZA comparison against picoPLAZA and PLAZA 2.5 resulted instead on a slightly higher amount of gene families split, 12.6% and 10.6% respectively.

Discussion

Taxonomic binning

Bacterial contamination is common in algal transcriptomic data obtained from field-collected material, as well as from cultures (Keeling *et al.*, 2014). Moreover, several green macroalgae engage in a mutualistic lifestyle with bacteria (Spoerner *et al.*, 2012; Wichard, 2015), or harbor intracellular bacteria (Hollants *et al.*, 2011; Hollants *et al.*, 2013; Aires *et al.*, 2015). Reliable methods to discriminate between contaminant and algal sequences are therefore fundamental.

Figure 2.6: Gene family size correlation – expressed green transcripts.

Each circle represents one or more gene family, the x-axis represents the number of genes from the reference *Chlamydomonas* transcriptome found expressed in that gene family, while the y-axis reports the corresponding green genes found in the eukaryotic fraction of the *de novo* assembled transcriptomes. The size of the circle is proportional to the gene families with that relative number of genomic and transcriptomic genes. The blue line corresponds to the regression line, the surrounding grey area indicates the 95% confidence interval. The corresponding equation is reported, together with the coefficient of correlation r^2 .

Figure 2.7: Gene family correlation between PLAZA builds.

pico02: picoPLAZA build. plaza2.5: PLAZA 2.5 build. chloro: chloroPLAZA 4.0 build. The builds were generated with sequences from Table 2.2 species.

We tested the efficiency in taxonomic profiling of an in-house method based on sequence similarity searches against the NCBI non-redundant protein database linked with taxonomic information, followed by a more detailed identification obtained with GhostKOALA. Similarity searches should handle properly the presence of the nuclear alternative genetic code, since they can perform gapped alignments. We showed that a single GhostKOALA analysis can be misleading, as is shown by the considerable amount of sequences not identified as “Plants” in well characterized green algal and land plant genomes (Figure 2.1). This is could be ascribed to the reference database GENES, which is a non-redundant collection of proteins from non-redundant pangenomes (Kanehisa *et al.*, 2014). However, the GENES database non-redundancy rule is extended up to the family level, and this should not result in mis-classification at the kingdom level. Moreover, GhostKOALA can give a useful estimate on the degree of contaminant sequences if datasets from the same species or from closely related species are analyzed. For example: difference in taxonomic distribution between *Chlamydomonas* genomic and transcriptomic sequences indicates the presence of contaminants in the transcriptomes, supported as well by different KO terms distribution in these two datasets. The fact that *Oltmannsiellopsis unicellularis* and *O.*

viridis have similar taxonomic distributions despite that their transcriptomes have been prepped and sequenced independently in different facilities, indicates that sequences classified as “Animal” could well be authentic *Oltmannsiellopsis* sequences. An additional explanation could come from the presence of undetected *Oltmannsiellopsidales* endo- or epiphytic organisms still not described nor characterized. Conversely, the taxonomic distribution of *Trentepohlia annulata* and *Cephaleuros parasiticus* sequences differs considerably from that of *Trentepohlia jolithus*, indicating that the latter transcriptome contains a considerably higher proportion of contaminant sequences, probably because the RNA was obtained from an environmental sample (Li *et al.*, 2014).

Frameshift correction

Frameshifts and premature stop codons in *de novo* assembled transcripts can represent real biological features in genes, which are corrected by RNA editing, as in mitochondrial transcripts of kinetoplastids or in chloroplast transcripts of dinoflagellates (Ochsenreiter & Hajduk, 2008; Mungpakdee *et al.*, 2014), or may represent pseudogenized genes. More often, however, frameshifts and premature stop codons result from sequencing or short read assembly errors. Frameshift errors are detrimental to the downstream comparative and phylogenetic analyses, and result in shorter and incorrectly translated peptides. In addition, due to specific drawbacks of each technology, each sequencing platform has its proper error profile which has to be taken into account (Glenn Travis, 2011; Nakamura *et al.*, 2011; Schirmer *et al.*, 2015; Schirmer *et al.*, 2016; Abnizova *et al.*, 2017). The 454 pyrosequencing technology is more prone to homopolymeric insertions, while Illumina technology is more prone to substitution: i.e. T to G transversions (Schirmer *et al.*, 2016), resulting in a theoretical higher chance to create frameshifts errors with 454 than with Illumina. Despite this, the 454 dataset did not show the highest rate of frameshifts, however, frameshift correction was most successful for the 454 datasets. Datasets generated with older Illumina chemistry did not perform worse than datasets generate with newer Illumina technologies and with longer reads. No correlation was found between depth of sequencing and percentage of frameshift transcripts, maybe because of the *in silico* read normalization step before assembling the Illumina reads with Trinity. These results may suggest that, at least for the datasets we analyzed, the putative frameshift

transcripts could be ascribed to random errors during the sequencing and assembly steps, rather than dependent on the technology of sequencing. However, for a proper benchmark of the origin of frameshift errors, the same RNA library should be sequenced on different sequencing machines, which was beyond the scope of this investigation.

Our frameshift correction approach is probably not perfectly suited for clades with alternative nuclear genetic codes, because of the unpredictable behavior on this kind of datasets. In fact, at the moment, TRAPID cannot handle multiple translation tables for coding sequences detection, nor can FrameDP for the frameshift correction step. On the other hand, these tools should still be efficient in detecting frameshift transcripts. In the presence of a reassigned internal stop codon, TRAPID is more likely to flag transcripts as “partial”, “quasi full-length” and “full-length”, depending on transcript length and position of the internal stop codon. Only transcripts with best hits to the same reference proteins on different reading frames are flagged as “frameshift”. FrameDP instead should treat internal stop codon as multiple events of frameshift that disrupt the coding sequence. This results into multiple random insertions of “N” nucleotides at the level of the internal stop codon, until the stop codon is converted to multiple ambiguous codons and the coding frame is restored. In principle, TRAPID and FrameDP should manage to correct frameshifts transcript also in the presence of alternative nuclear genetic code, although the amount of artificial insertions is unpredictable. On the other hand, there is no obvious or logic explanation for the lack of correction of *Trentepohlia annulata* frameshift transcripts. Tools designed to handle alternative nuclear genetic codes are required to confidently detect and correct frameshifts, and, at best of our knowledge, still missing.

Transcriptomes gene space completeness evaluation

Three different methods used to evaluate the completeness of transcriptome gene space, coreGF, BUSCO and eggNOG-mapper, gave complementary overviews on the gene-space completeness of the transcriptomes and of the genomes. While coreGF and BUSCO methods gave comparable results, coreGF was found to have higher sensitivity. coreGF reference database is six time larger than BUSCO (1,815 coreGF proteins against 330 BUSCO proteins) and it is populated almost exclusively with green

algae genomes. This represent a reference database well suited to assess the gene space completeness of a green algal transcriptome. The BUSCO database we used is a collection of 330 quasi-single-copy orthologous genes shared by all eukaryotes. There is an Embryophyta-specific BUSCO database, but it is unbalanced towards land plants and not representative for green algae. Therefore, coreGF results as a more sensitive approach to evaluate gene space completeness in green algae. In our analysis, this difference resulted evident for some species (e.g.: *Pseudochlorella pringsheimii*), that despite having a completeness score close to 1 was missing almost 30% of BUSCO genes.

One may think that BUSCO genes are related to extremely conserved functions among eukaryotes (such as DNA replication and repair), and might not be always expressed to levels high enough for granting the detection of the transcripts. Several coreGF proteins instead, since they were determined exclusively from green algae, are probably involved in the photosynthetic processes and possibly expressed at high levels in metabolic active algae, which grant their detection during RNA sequencing. Moreover, coreGF method has the strong advantage of reporting the percentage of reference transcripts covered by 50% and 90% of their length, while BUSCO only provides a qualitative score for the transcript completeness. Recovery of full-length transcripts is a desirable outcome of RNA-seq sequencing and it is required for successful downstream analyses: the coverage score is therefore a fundamental estimate of integrity of conserved transcripts.

The eggNOG mapper is a comprehensive annotation method that can assign KO terms, gene ontology (GO) terms, KEGG pathways and cluster of orthologous groups (COG) functional categories to query sequences based on sequence similarity to precomputed clusters of orthologous groups (Huerta-Cepas *et al.*, 2017). To evaluate the completeness of a transcriptome, we detected the fraction of KO terms associated with chloroNOG and virNOG clusters identified in the transcriptomes. The KO terms identified in the different transcriptomes revealed useful insights on the completeness and on the degree of putative novel/contaminating sequences in the transcriptomes that coreGF and BUSCO methods would miss. On the other hand, many coreGF genes are not associated with a KO term: most species have coreGF score close to 1, while most of the Chlorophyta/Viridiplantae KO terms may be absent (e.g.: *Cephaleuros parasiticus* and *Trentepohlia annulata* transcriptomes). This observation is consistent

with the annotation of “green cut proteins”, a set of 597 nucleus-encoded proteins conserved in all photosynthetic organisms, 50% of which are not yet characterized (Karpowicz *et al.*, 2011).

Despite these three approaches rely on distinct reference databases and they are therefore not directly comparable, their concurrent use should grant a wide overview on transcripts and gene space completeness of a transcriptome. Moreover, the complementarity of the reference databases may hint toward which genes/functions are present and the possible presence of contaminant sequences

Depth of sequencing: transcriptome completeness and gene family size correlation

The analyses of transcripts and gene space completeness at increasing depth of sequencing indicated 40M reads as the depth of sequencing where most of the measured metrics reached a plateau. Despite N50 values and number of assembled transcripts increased with higher depths of sequencing, adding more reads seems not to improve drastically the recovery of conserved genes, and, instead, it results to be detrimental for certain metrics. At higher depth of sequencing, in fact, more BUSCO genes were identified as duplicated, and gene family sizes correlation between reference and *de novo* assembled sequences indicated a biased toward *de novo* sequence overestimation. The results from the gene space completeness analysis pointed towards an almost complete gene space when compared to the reference genome at all the depth of sequencing analyzed (8M-80M reads), but higher sequencing depth resulted in longer transcripts and a larger percentage of reference genes length covered.

This analysis represents a good starting point to model the relationship between depth of sequencing, gene space completeness evaluation and orthology inference. However, it is severely hampered by being restricted to *Chlamydomonas* only. It is difficult to predict how this relationship scale from *Chlamydomonas* 111 Mb genome coding for almost 18 thousand genes to the transcriptome of a green alga for which estimates on genome and gene space sizes are not available. The predictive power of this analysis would definitely benefit by being repeated on all available green algal genomes.

Effect of partial data on Orthology inference and gene family size correlation

A desirable feature of comparative transcriptomics is the possibility to compare gene family sizes between different organisms to elucidate and unveil the genetic underpinning and evolution of biological properties. Key biological innovations are often associated with gene family expansion, shrinking, gain or loss (Gardner *et al.*, 2002; Martens *et al.*, 2008; Pombert *et al.*, 2014; Dunn *et al.*, 2018). While gene family comparisons are somewhat easily executed in comparative genomic studies, it is not trivial to perform them based on transcriptomic data given that *de novo* assembled transcriptomes only partially represent the gene space of the corresponding genomes.

Our analyses on gene family reconstruction from expressed transcripts and expressed green transcripts indicate that transcriptomic data generally overestimate gene family sizes. Moreover, the corresponding correlation coefficient values were relatively low ($r^2 = 0.498-0.632$). This trend is observed virtually at any sequencing depth, and it could be ascribed to the redundancy of the transcriptomics datasets, i.e.: multiple transcripts are assembled for each genomic locus. Furthermore, *Chlamydomonas* is suited for this gene family size correlation assessment, since its transcription and ploidy level is much simpler if compared to other eukaryotes (e.g.: higher plants or higher mammals), and only 10% of its transcripts undergo alternative splicing (1,785 out of 17,741 protein-coding genes). Allelic variants and alternative spliced transcripts cannot account for the overestimation of gene family sizes observed in the *de novo* assembled sequences. Thus, together with the intrinsic incomplete gene space represented in the transcriptome, these results support the idea that transcriptomic data generally are not well suited for analyses of gene family expansion, and gene gain and loss.

These results contrast with the accuracy of gene family inference of PLAZA 4.0. This method in fact is robust and does not suffer from the majority of data being fragmented sequences during the gene family reconstruction step. Perhaps, complete sequences from the 15 genomes drive the faithful inference of orthologous groups, despite representing only 30% of the total sequences. Redundant sequences from *de novo* assembled transcriptomes are likely to be grouped in the same gene family and not to

Figure 2.8: Schematic overview of the transcriptomic pipeline for green algal transcriptomes.

Detailed information on the workflow steps are reported on the text.

influence the orthology inference process. Instead, the minimal (2%) increase of split gene families observed in chloroPLAZA (Figure 2.7) are probably ascribed to partial transcripts assigned to the wrong gene families due to similar domain composition.

A transcriptomic pipeline for green algae

The information acquired during our analyses was used to build a *de novo* assembly and annotation pipeline. After quality control, RNA-seq reads are first assembled, then, the redundancy in the transcriptome is reduced using CD-HIT EST with stringent parameters. Nrprot taxonomic binning approach is used to discard bacterial sequences and sequences with no similarity with known proteins. TRAPID and FrameDP are used to correct frameshift errors and to predict open reading frames of each transcript with an orthology-guided approach based on *Chlamydomonas* proteome. A custom java plugin allows TRAPID do uses multiple translation tables during Open reading frame prediction, accounting for nuclear alternative, chloroplast and mitochondrial genetic code. Open reading frames are combined with the genomic coding sequences to build a custom PLAZA 4.0 instance, which is used to circumscribe gene families, which can be used in phylotranscriptomic analyses in Chapter 3: “Reconstruction of the early diversification of green seaweeds” (Figure 2.8).

Materials and Methods

Dataset retrieval and RNA extraction

55 species of green algae were sampled belonging to the major clades of the Chlorophyta and Streptophyta. Data consisted of 15 genomes and 40 transcriptomes; 9 transcriptomes were generated for this study, while the remaining data were retrieved from publicly available repositories (Table 2.1).

Acetabularia acetabulum, *Oltmannsiellopsis viridis* and *Scotinosphaera lemnae* cultures were grown at 20 °C and 12-h light/12-h dark cycle in Ace-25 medium (Hunt & Mandoli, 1996) and 1.5% agar-solidified Bold Basal medium (Bischoff, 1963), respectively. *Marsupiomonas* sp., *Pedinomonas minor* and the pedinophyte strain YPF-701 (NIES Microbial Culture Collection strain NIES-2566) were cultured in Guillard's F/2 medium at 20 °C and 14-h light/10-h dark cycle. For *Ostreobium* sp. HV05042, *Halimeda discoidea* and *Codium fragile* freshly collected material was used for RNA extraction. Collection details are given in Verbruggen et al. (2017). Unicellular microscopic algae cultures (*Marsupiomonas* sp., *Oltmannsiellopsis viridis*, *Pedinomonas minor*, pedinophyte strain YPF-701 and *Scotinosphaera lemnae*) were harvested during their exponential phase. Whole macroscopic seaweed specimens were harvested from cultures (*Acetabularia acetabulum*) or collected in their natural environment (*Codium fragile*, *Halimeda discoidea* and *Ostreobium* sp. HV05042) and ground in liquid nitrogen for RNA extraction. RNA extractions follow Palmer (1982). RNA quality and quantity were assessed with Qubit and Nanodrop spectrophotometer, and integrity was assessed with a Bioanalyzer 2100. RNA-seq libraries were sequenced as reported in Table 2.3.

Transcriptome Assembly and Taxonomic filtering

At the time of the experiment, only pre-assembled transcriptomes of *Acrosiphonia* sp., *Blastophysa rhizopus* and *Caulerpa taxifolia* transcriptomes were available: Therefore, these datasets were retrieved from the respective sources reported in Table 2.1. All the remaining assemblies were performed in house starting from the raw reads on a custom semi-automated pipeline. The pipeline consisted of the following steps. Quality of the raw reads were assessed with FastQC v.0.10.1

(<http://www.bioinformatics.babraham.ac.uk>, last accessed March 01, 2017). Low-quality reads (average Phreds quality score below 20) and low quality read ends were trimmed with Fastx v.0.0.13 (https://github.com/agordon/fastx_toolkit, last accessed March 01, 2017). Trimmed reads shorter than 30 bp were discarded.

Transcriptome *de novo* assembly of *Botryococcus braunii*, *Chlorokybus atmophyticus*, *Ulva linza* (Roche 454 data) were performed with CLC Genomics Workbench version 7.5.1 (<http://www.clcbio.com>, last accessed on June 06, 2017), using a word size of 63 and standard parameters. Transcriptome *de novo* assembly for the remaining species were performed with Trinity 2.1.1 (Grabherr *et al.*, 2011), in SE or PE mode were appropriate depending on the RNA-seq library type, after *in silico* reads normalization.

For each transcriptome, transcripts were clustered with CD-HIT-EST v. 4.6.1 (Li & Godzik, 2006) with the following parameters: -c 0.975, -d 0, -p 1 and -M 0, and the longest one was retained as representative of the cluster. The eukaryotic fraction of each transcriptome was identified with sequence similarity searches using Tera-BLAST DeCypher (Active Motif, USA) against the NCBI non-redundant protein database combined with the NCBI Taxonomy information of the top ten BLAST hits (hereafter: nrprot), where a hit to Eukaryotic sequences was sufficient to assign the transcript to the “eukaryotic bin”. Transcripts were therefore assigned to “eukaryotic”, “bacterial”, “no hit” bins based on the outcome of search. To evaluate the amount of residual bacterial contaminants still present in nrprot and to circumscribe a fraction of green transcripts, the coding regions of eukaryotic transcripts were predicted with TRAPID and translated into the corresponding amino acid sequences with transeq algorithm from EMBOSS 6.6.0 (Rice *et al.*, 2000), using the appropriate translation table where necessary. The resulting peptides were processed with GhostKOALA (Kanehisa *et al.*, 2016). For each peptide having the best scoring hit in *Viridiplantae*, the corresponding transcript was flagged as “green”. Coding sequences from the genomes in Table 2.1 were processed as well in a similar manner as control sequences.

Figure 2.9: Schematic overview of the frameshift correction workflow.

Detailed information on the workflow steps are reported on the text.

Frameshift correction

Frameshift correction performance (Figure 2.9) was evaluated on the eukaryotic fraction of the transcriptomes of Table 2.2. Each transcriptome was analyzed with TRAPID (Van Bel *et al.*, 2013). For each transcriptome, a subset of transcripts with potential frameshift was predicted, based on the concordance with orthologous sequences as predicted with TRAPID. This subset was corrected with a local step of frameshift correction in FrameDP 1.2.2 (Gouzy *et al.*, 2009), using the *Chlamydomonas* 4.0 proteome. The corrected subset, together with transcripts that were not classified as potentially having a frameshift, were analyzed again with the TRAPID pipeline to evaluate the efficiency of the frameshift detection and correction.

Transcriptome completeness evaluation

Evaluation of transcriptome completeness was performed by evaluating the gene space completeness of the genomes and the eukaryotic fraction of transcriptome with three different methods (Figure 2.10): coreGF score (Veeckman *et al.*, 2016); BUSCO (Simão *et al.*, 2015) and eggNOG-mapper (Huerta-Cepas *et al.*, 2017). Despite that each method relies on a different set of reference sequences, the underlying idea is conserved: estimate the portion of the reference database represented in the query sequences, thus, derive the *bona fide* completeness of the query itself. Where

possible, the reference dataset should include closely related species, to increase the likelihood to represent the most complete (likely) gene space possible of the query species.

For the coreGF evaluation method, transcripts and genomic coding sequences were searched using Tera-BLAST™ DeCypher against pico-PLAZA v2.0 proteome, which is composed by genome sequences of 10 green algae, 3 land plants, one glaucophyte and 5 stramenopiles (Vandepoele *et al.*, 2013). A set of 1,815 homologous core gene families were identified with tribe-MCL (Enright *et al.*, 2002). A core gene family is defined as a gene family shared among all the Chlorophyta genomes present in pico-PLAZA 2.0. Each transcript or coding sequence was assigned to a certain gene family based on its top 5 hit, following a majority consensus rule. Finally, the GFscore was calculated as the sum of each core family identified, counted with a weight equal to one divided by the average family size.

For the BUSCO analysis, the transcripts and genomic coding sequences were searched with BUSCO 3.0.1 (Simão *et al.*, 2015) against the eukaryotic ortholog groups present on OrthoDB v9 database (Zdobnov *et al.*, 2017), using the “transcriptome” mode (flag -m tran).

For the eggNOG-mapper search (Huerta-Cepas *et al.*, 2017), three distinct sets of non-supervised orthologous groups (NOG) clusters were tested: Chlorophyta NOGs (chloroNOG), Viridiplantae NOGs (virNOG), and all the NOGs present in the emapper database v. 4.5.1 (bacterial and viral NOGs included). The coding sequences of genomes and transcriptomes were compared to the chloroNOG, virNOG and NOG clusters. Searches against chloroNOG and virNOG were run with HMMer profiles (Eddy, 2011) available at the emapper database, using optimized memory searches (flag --usemem). For the sake of speed, searches against the whole NOG clusters were run with DIAMOND 0.9.9, flag -m diamond (Buchfink *et al.*, 2014). To evaluate the gene space completeness predicted with eggNOG searches, we identified the number of KEGG Orthology (KO) terms (Kanehisa *et al.*, 2014) that were assigned to each subset by the searches. To define the total KO terms associated to chloroNOG and virNOG clusters, the protein used for populating the clusters were searched

Figure 2.10: Schematic overview of the gene space completeness evaluation workflow.

Detailed information on the workflow steps are reported on the text.

against chloroNOG and virNOG clusters respectively, and the resulting KO terms identified were set as KO terms associated to the clusters.

Depth of sequencing: transcriptome completeness and gene family size correlation

Data retrieval, transcriptome assembly and frameshift correction

For the depth of sequencing evaluation, the *Chlamydomonas reinhardtii* reference genome v.5.5 and corresponding full length transcripts were retrieved from Phytozome, <https://phytozome.jgi.doe.gov/pz/portal.html> (Goodstein *et al.*, 2012). The SRR353973 RNA-seq library was retrieved from the Short Read Archive, <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/sra/?term=SRR353973> (Leinonen *et al.*, 2011), which represents the largest RNA-seq library available to our knowledge for *Chlamydomonas reinhardtii*.

The workflow to process this dataset was similar as described above. Briefly, quality of the 83M 2x101 bp PE raw reads were assessed with FastQC v.0.10.1. Low-quality reads (average Phred quality score below 20) were discarded and low-quality 3' ends of the reads were trimmed with Fastx v.0.0.13. After trimming, reads shorter than 30

bp were discarded. 80,660,120 PE reads were retained after trimming and filtering. Ten subsets representing 10-100% of the trimmed reads were randomly selected from the total retained reads (Table S2.1) to mimic comparable RNA-seq libraries with increasing sequencing depth using a custom python script <https://github.com/brentp/bio-playground/blob/master/reads-utils/select-random-pairs.py>. Each subset of PE reads was independently assembled with Trinity v. 2.1.1. Trinity assemblies were performed with standard parameters after *in silico* read normalization (flag --normalize_reads).

After assembly, the resulting transcripts were clustered with CD-HIT-EST 4.6.1 using the following parameters: -c 0.975, -d 0, -p 1 and -M 0. The longest member for each cluster was used as the representative for the cluster for downstream analyses. The eukaryotic fraction for each assembly was identified as described above. Transcripts classified as "eukaryotic" were further processed in TRAPID for identifying coding regions and correct putative frameshift errors. A fraction of green transcripts was identified with GhostKOALA. After processing with TRAPID, the transcripts and the corresponding coding regions of each assembly were examined to assess transcriptome completeness as described in the previous paragraph.

Gene family size correlation

To evaluate the members of a gene family *de novo* assembled in a transcriptome with the real number of members as identified in the corresponding fully sequenced genome, we determined homologous gene families (HOM) in a similar process to the PLAZA 4.0 build (Figure 2.11). We build a custom protein dataset by first removing *Chlamydomonas* sequences from picoPLAZA proteome and by adding the remaining picoPLAZA proteins to all predicted proteins from the sequenced genomes of *Gonium pectorale* (Hanschen *et al.*, 2016), *Auxenochlorella protothecoides* v. 1.0 (Gao *et al.*, 2014), *Asterochloris* sp. Cgr/DA1pho v2.0, *Ulva mutabilis* v.3.0 (De Clerck *et al.*, 2018), *Selaginella moellendorffii* v. 1.0 (Banks *et al.*, 2011). Then *C. reinhardtii* complete reference transcriptome v.5.5 was retrieved from JGI, and only reference *Chlamydomonas reinhardtii* transcripts that were found expressed at a certain depth of sequencing were added to the custom protein database. For each depth of sequencing, reference *Chlamydomonas* expressed genes were identified by aligning

the reads the reference transcriptome with Kallisto v. 0.43.0 (Bray *et al.*, 2016). Only transcripts with a transcript per million (TMP) value > 5 were considered as expressed. This resulted in 10 reference proteome datasets, one for each depth of sequencing (8M-80M reads), composed by complete proteomes and amino acid sequences of the reference *Chlamydomonas* transcripts found expressed at that depth of sequencing. Then, for each depth of sequencing, *Chlamydomonas de novo* assembled eukaryotic and green transcripts that were found expressed were identified and added to the corresponding reference protein databases. The corresponding amino acid sequences of the potential coding regions were deduced with the transeq algorithm present in the EMBOSS package. For each depth of sequencing tested, the deduced peptides were added to corresponding reference proteome database. For each protein database, all-against-all sequence similarity searches were computed with DIAMOND, with 4,000 max target sequences and using the flag --more-sensitive. To define the gene families, the sequence similarity results were then clustered with Tribe-MCL v. 10-201 with the following parameters: -l 2, -scheme 4. For each gene family, the members from the *de novo* assembled transcriptome and the members from reference *Chlamydomonas* transcriptome were counted, and the counts plotted. Only gene families with members both in the transcriptome and in the genome were considered in this analysis.

Effect of partial data on orthology inference

We tested the impact of introducing partial sequences (i.e.: *de novo* assembled transcripts) in the inference of homologous gene families by the PLAZA pipeline (all-against-all sequence similarity search followed by Tribe-MCL clustering). First of all, transcriptomes and genomes for the 55 species reported in Table 2.1 were processed through the pipeline described in this chapter (eukaryotic filtering, frameshift correction). The longest coding frame was detected with a custom java script plugged into TRAPID using four different translation tables (1, 6, 11 and 16), to take into account the alternative nuclear genetic codes (Cocquyt *et al.*, 2010a), as well as the chloroplast

Figure 2.11: Schematic overview of the depth of sequencing evaluation workflow.

Detailed information on the workflow steps are reported on the text.

and mitochondrial translation tables. Briefly, for each transcript coding frames were predicted with each of the four translation tables. Then, for each transcript, the longest coding sequences detected was retained for the downstream analysis, and the corresponding translation table recorded. Concordance with orthologous sequences predicted by the TRAPID pipeline by sequence similarity searches was also taken into account. Each transcript was translated into the corresponding amino acid sequences with the transeq algorithm from the EMBOSS package, using the appropriate translation table. The resulting predicted peptides were processed with an in-house instance of PLAZA4.0 (Van Bel *et al.*, 2018), named ChloroPLAZA.

Figure 2.12: Schematic overview of the effect of partial data on orthology inference workflow.

Detailed information on the workflow steps are reported on the text.

Slim versions of picoPLAZA (build A), PLAZA2.5 (build B) and ChloroPLAZA (build C) protein databases were created, where HOM gene families containing orphan genes were removed. picoPLAZA and PLAZA2.5 (Build A and Build B, respectively) constitutes reference datasets constructed from genomic data, while ChloroPLAZA (Build C) represents the dataset composed by majority of transcriptomic data to test.

For the analysis, only HOM families containing one or more genes from *Arabidopsis thaliana*, *Chlamydomonas reinhardtii*, *Micromonas pusilla*, *Ostreococcus tauri*, *Physcomitrella patens* or *Volvox carteri* were selected, since for these species the genome versions to build the databases were identical and gene identifiers were conserved between builds. As a positive control, build A was tested against build B, and vice versa. To test the effect of partial data on orthology inference, build A and build B were independently tested against build C (Figure 2.12). For each of the selected HOM families, each gene from *Arabidopsis thaliana*, *Chlamydomonas reinhardtii*, *Micromonas pusilla*, *Ostreococcus tauri*, *Physcomitrella patens* or *Volvox carteri* of a dataset was searched and identified in the HOM families of the test dataset and the number of HOM families retrieved is recorder. The resulting rate of correlation for each HOM family was calculated as: $1/(\text{number of Hit HOM identified})$, where 1 is the highest score and indicate a perfect 1 to 1 correlation, while values between 0 and 1 indicate that genes from a HOM family were found in two or more HOM families in the test dataset.

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Supplementary Information

Figure S2.1: Gene space completeness evaluated with eggNOG mapper.

KO terms associated with chloroNOG clusters identified for the species Table 2.2. KO terms were grouped based on their function.

Figure S2.4: Taxonomic binning as assigned by GhostKOALA.

Pie charts report the proportion of the taxonomic bin assigned to transcriptome assembly. These results are in contrast with the GhostKOALA output for *Chlamydomonas* genomic CDSs (Figure 2.1).

Figure S2.5: Depth of sequencing and gene space completeness evaluation.

(A) Bar plot illustrating the GFscore and the corresponding Reference coverage scores (50% and 90% of reference genes covered) respectively. (B) The percentage of the BUSCO genes identified as complete, duplicated, fragmented or missing in the assemblies and in the reference genome of the total 303 BUSCO eukaryotic single-gene orthologs is reported. (C) KO terms associated with chloroNOG, virNOG, NOG clusters identified at each depth of sequencing.

Table S2.1: Overview of the assembly metrics.

		Assembly metrics						
		before CD-HIT		after CD-HIT		euk fraction		
subset	# PE reads	# seq	N50 (bp)	# seq	N50 (bp)	# euk	%euk	N50 euk (bp)
8M	8,066,012	72,378	827	50,350	770	32,091	63.74	939
16M	16,132,024	92,565	951	62,495	909	40,593	64.95	1,112
24M	24,198,036	106,092	1,020	70,465	984	45,691	64.84	1,225
32M	32,264,048	116,322	1,066	76,399	1,041	49,328	64.57	1,287
40M	40,330,060	124,202	1,093	81,202	1,081	52,103	64.16	1,334
48M	48,396,072	131,244	1,124	85,118	1,122	54,213	63.69	1,391
56M	56,462,084	136,644	1,151	88,385	1,155	56,159	63.54	1,433
64M	64,528,096	142,075	1,180	91,436	1,189	57,764	63.17	1,471
72M	72,594,108	146,736	1,196	94,338	1,220	59,526	63.10	1,502
80M	80,660,120	150,504	1,206	96,490	1,233	60,694	62.90	1,525
before CD-HIT: transcriptome metrics before sequence clustering with CD-HIT EST after CD-HIT: transcriptome metrics after sequence clustering with CD-HIT EST euk fraction: metrics of the eukaryotic fraction % euk: percentage of transcripts (after CD-HIT) identified as eukaryotic								